

CHAPTER 6

General Conclusions and Future Scope

This research work was initiated with the motive to investigate different physical properties particularly stability, electronic structure, and transport behavior of transition metal-based double perovskites. Furthermore, it is important to figure out the physical phenomenon behind the properties displayed by this class of material. As it would help to understand how properties especially electronic and magnetic would alter if the constituents in the composition are changed. The large prospect of applications of DPs can be attributed to a wide variety of magneto-electronic profile, high-temperature stability, and high corrosion resistance. In this report, we have not only studied the already known DPs but also designed some new members of the family suitable for photovoltaic, spintronics and thermoelectric technologies. The newly designed materials are first investigated for stability and thereafter explored electronic, optical and transport properties of these materials. The existing set of calculations were performed within the density functional theory (DFT) by employing the full potential augmented plane wave method as implemented in the WIEN2k code. The conclusive remarks of all chapters and general conclusions of the work are described below.

Chapter 1 gives an introduction about photovoltaic and thermoelectric energy conversion. This chapter starts with a discussion about the need for energy conversion materials and definition of photovoltaic materials. Also, we have discussed the significance of photovoltaic technology over non-renewable energy sources. Later, we have discussed about characteristics of solar cells. In addition to this, the PCE along with its relation to the material's properties is discussed. Next, we have defined the thermoelectric device and the efficiency of TEG, figure of merit, lead-free halide double perovskites materials and their properties. Thereafter, we have discussed about problem with thermoelectric parameters and approach to enhance figure of merit. Finally, we have discussed about structural, electronic, optical and thermoelectric properties of lead-free halide double perovskites. Moreover, the importance of lead-free halide double perovskites as photovoltaic and thermoelectric materials are discussed.

Chapter 2 provides a brief theory of the methods used in the thesis to study the electronic, phonon and transport properties of compounds. It starts with a description of DFT, then the Kohn-Sham equations and their self-consistent solution are briefly discussed. Next, the various XC functionals are discussed in subsection. The theory of semiclassical transport is given in next section. In the next section, we have discussed about phonon calculation. Then, the first-principles calculation techniques of phonon properties are summarized. In the last, the details SCAPS-1D simulation and its working steps are mentioned.

In Chapter 3, We have carried out details studies on $\text{Cs}_2\text{Tl}(\text{As/Sb})\text{I}_6$. The obtained band gap values show that they are outstanding material for green energy technology. Further studies revealed that they have outshining optoelectronic properties required for green energy technology. Moreover, a large value of electrical conductivity, ultra-low thermal conductivity and large value of figure of merit (ZT) exposed their potential for thermoelectric generators and refrigerators.

In Chapter 4, there is a systematic study on electronic, optical, structural, photovoltaic and thermoelectric properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ by using SCAPS-1D and DFT simulation. The obtained thermodynamic stability of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is confirmed by its negative formation energy. The details of electronic property show the direct band gap nature of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ with a gap value of 0.93 eV (with mBJ + SOC). In addition, the predicted optical properties confirmed the excellent conductivity and high absorption coefficient of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$. Furthermore, a solar cell having the structure of $\text{ITO}/\text{SnO}_2/\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6/\text{Au}$ was made which shows a maximum power conversion efficiency of 16.35 %. Moreover, the higher ZT value of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is coming from small k with large σ . Thus, $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is suitable for green energy technology.

In Chapter 5, we have studied the magnetic and spin-based thermoelectric properties of K_2WX_6 [X=Cl, Br]. The spin-polarized band structure along with density of states shows show the half-metallic nature of both compounds. Further, the calculated spin based optical properties shows that the down channel of both compounds is having higher order of absorption coefficient and low reflectivity which tells that we can used them for high efficiency solar cell

by polarizing in down channel direction. The thermoelectric parameters are calculated to examine the suitability in spin based Seebeck effect. The high σ , S, PF, ZT and low thermal along the spin down channel demonstrated that we can use them for high efficiency thermoelectricity by polarizing in down channel direction.

Chapter 6 summarizes the thesis, with a brief overview of the significant conclusions drawn and gives direction for future work.

6.1 Future Scope

Apart from the above-said results, there are still some pending issues and queries, which have to be addressed yet. Since the thermoelectric parameters can be decoupled via nano-structuring which allows an increase in Seebeck coefficient without decreasing electrical conductivity, so these materials need to be investigated in that range. The heat transportation is done by both electrons and phonons, we have not included the phonon effect on transport properties in this work. Moreover, we have not included the effect of doping and strain on the overall physical properties of these materials. Also, some of the perovskites are predicted first time in this work which needs experimental verifications. In the net shell, the present results would be useful in the extra exploration of these materials in the future.